

MASTER CROSSWALK

Crosswalk of SSA criteria of mental functioning to related ICF b and d codes

This document correlates policy language from the United States Social Security Administration (SSA) disability determination for adults with mental disorders, with related activity-functioning codes from the International Classification of Functioning, Disability and Health (ICF) (World Health Organization, 2001). The purpose of this document was to support our work in natural language processing (NLP) to identify and extract the language of functioning, documented in clinical records, at the ICF level of Activities and Participation. Recognizing that clinical documentation of mental functioning information can often be written at the level of body functions, we therefore include body function (ICF b-codes) in addition to activity functioning (ICF d-codes) in this crosswalk to help annotators decide how mentions of mental functions and mental functioning might be represented in codes for the Activities and Participation component of the ICF. The ICF Activities and Participation component has both activity and participation codes. As our work was focused on annotating activity functioning rather than participation, we used ICF activity codes from chapters d1-d7 and excluded what we delineated as participation codes from the d8 and d9 chapters.

This Master Crosswalk is intended as a supplementary resource to the annotation guidelines that we have published in the Activity domains of Communication & Cognition (ComCog) (NIH CC RMD Epidemiology & Biostatistics Section, 2025a), Mobility (NIH CC RMD Epidemiology & Biostatistics Section, 2025c), Self-Care & Domestic Life (SCDL) (NIH CC RMD Epidemiology & Biostatistics Section, 2025d), and Interpersonal Interactions and Relationships (IPIR) (NIH CC RMD Epidemiology & Biostatistics Section, 2025b).

The Master Crosswalk differs from the appendices in the ComCog and IPIR annotation guidelines that provide crosswalks to the SSA mental functioning criteria that are specific only to these Activity domains and thus did not include all SSA mental functioning criteria. This Master Crosswalk is not domain specific and represents a more comprehensive crosswalk, which was established prior to the development of the annotation guidelines mentioned above, to ensure that all SSA policy language related to mental health was represented in ICF codes that annotators used for coding mental functioning information. This crosswalk is intended to be a “one-stop shop” where the complete SSA mental functioning criteria is mapped to all ICF Activity codes that are represented by ComCog (ICF d1-d3 codes), Mobility (ICF d4 codes), SCDL (ICF d5 and d6 codes), and IPIR (ICF d7 codes).

Policy language included in this document stem from two SSA sources: (1) The paragraph B and paragraph C criteria from the listings of impairments for mental disorders – adult (Social Security Administration, 2023), and (2) the Mental Residual Functional Capacity (RFC) Assessment (Social Security Administration, 2024). The paragraph B and C criteria are used during Step 3 of SSA’s sequential determination process to evaluate whether claimants meet SSA’s definition of disability. The mental RFC is used during Steps 4 and 5 of the determination process and records a summary of conclusions derived from evidence in a claimant’s file that rates the presence and severity of mental limitations. These criteria and areas of mental functioning used by SSA are outlined below.

The four areas, referred to as the **B Criteria**, in SSA’s **Listings for Mental Disorders - Adult** are:

- B1. Understand, remember, or apply information
- B2. Interact with others
- B3. Concentrate, persist, or maintain pace
- B4. Adapt or manage oneself

The **C1 Criterion** in SSA’s Listings for Mental Disorders - Adult includes:

- Ongoing reliance on medical treatment, mental health therapy, psychosocial support(s),
- or a highly structured setting(s), to diminish the symptoms and signs of the mental disorder.

The **C2 Criterion** in SSA’s Listings for Mental Disorders - Adult includes:

- Minimal capacity to adapt to changes in one’s environment
- Minimal capacity to adapt to demands that are not already part of one’s daily life
- Changes or increased demands have led to exacerbation of symptoms and signs and to deterioration in functioning, i.e., unable to function outside of one’s home or a more restrictive setting, without substantial psychosocial supports.

The four areas of the **Mental Residual Functional Capacity (RFC) Assessment** are:

- A. Understanding and Memory
- B. Sustained concentration and Persistence
- C. Social Interaction
- D. Adaptation

Table 1 is an overview that lays out the criteria from each SSA policy source along with the related ICF body functions and activities and participation codes.

Table 1: Overview of SSA Mental Functioning criteria and ICF sources included in the Master Crosswalk

SSA Mental Functioning criteria sources			ICF sources
B Criteria in SSA Adult Mental Disorders	C Criteria in SSA Adult Mental Disorders	Mental Residual Functional Capacity Assessment	ICF Components, Domains, Chapters, and Codes
B1. Understand, remember, or apply information B2. Interact with others B3. Concentrate, persist, or maintain pace B4. Adapt or manage oneself	C1. Ongoing reliance on <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • medical treatment, • mental health therapy, • psychosocial support(s), • highly structured setting(s) 	A. Understanding and Memory B. Sustained concentration and Persistence C. Social Interaction D. Adaptation	ICF Component: Body Functions Domain: Mental Functions <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Global mental functions • Specific Mental functions ICF Component: Activities and Participation

	<p>C2. Minimal capacity to adapt to</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • changes in one’s environment • Demands that are not already part of one’s daily life. • Changes or increased demands have led to exacerbation of symptoms and signs and to deterioration in functioning • i.e. unable to function outside of one’s home or a more restrictive setting, without substantial psychosocial supports 		<p>Domain: Learning and Applying Knowledge (Chapter 1)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Basic Knowledge • Applying Knowledge <p>Domain: General Tasks and Demands (Chapter 2)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Undertaking a single task • Undertaking multiple tasks • Carrying out a daily routine • Handling stress and other psychological demands <p>Domain: Communication (Chapter 3)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Communicating – receiving • Communicating – producing <p>Domain: Mobility (Chapter 4)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Moving around using transportation <p>Domain: Self-care (Chapter 5)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Looking after one’s health <p>Domain: Interpersonal Interactions and Relationships (Chapter 7)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • General interpersonal interactions • Particular interpersonal relationships
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Though the language from SSA’s B and C criteria and Mental RFC Assessment are similar, there are some differences. Therefore, language from the *SSA’s B and C criteria* is shown in blue font and language from SSA’s *Mental RFC Assessment* is shown in green font in Tables 2-7. All SSA policy language is cross-walked to ICF codes in the Body Function (b codes) and Activities and Participation (d codes) components. Bolded codes are parent ICF 3-digit codes. The 4-digit ICF codes are listed to give more specificity and conceptual clarity to SSA mental functioning concepts.

Table 2 includes the mapping of the B1 Criterion and area A of the Mental RFC, which refer to the abilities to learn, recall, and use information to perform work activities, to ICF codes.

Table 2: SSA B1 Criterion and Mental RFC Area A: Understand, remember, or apply information

12.00 Mental Disorders - Adult	ICF Codes	
SSA B1 Criterion	ICF b codes	ICF d codes
Mental RFC Assessment - A	Body Function	Activities Functioning
Understand information	b117 intellectual functions b156 Perceptual functions b1670 Reception of language	d140 Learning to read d163 Thinking d310 Communicating - receiving spoken messages d315 Communicating - receiving nonverbal messages d3152 Communicating with-receiving-drawings and photographs d320 Communicating - receiving formal sign language d325 Communicating - receiving written messages
Remember information	b144 Memory functions b1440 Short-term memory b1441 Long-term memory b1442 Retrieval and processing of memory b1443 Working memory	d210 Undertaking a single task d220 Undertaking multiple tasks d163 Thinking
Apply information	b144 Memory functions	d210 Undertaking a single task d220 Undertaking multiple tasks
Abilities to learn information to perform work activities	b140 Attention functions b144 Memory functions	d155 Acquiring skills d137 Acquiring concepts d138 Acquiring information d160 Focusing attention
Abilities recall information to perform work activities The ability to remember locations and work-like procedures The ability to remember very short and simple instructions The ability to remember detailed instructions.	b144 Memory functions b1440 Short-term memory b1442 Retrieval and processing of memory b1441 Long-term memory	d210 Undertaking a single task d220 Undertaking multiple tasks

Abilities to use information to perform work activities	b144 Memory functions b164 Higher-level cognitive functions b177 Intellectual functions	d163 Thinking d210 Undertaking a single task d220 Undertaking multiple tasks d2301 Managing daily routine d2302 Completing the daily routine
understanding and learning terms, instructions, procedures The ability to understand very short and simple instructions The ability to understand detailed instructions.	b144 Memory function b1640 Abstraction b1670 Reception of language b177 Intellectual functions	d138 Acquiring information d166 Reading d310 Communicating with - receiving spoken messages d3100 Communicating with - receiving simple spoken messages d3101 Communicating with - receiving complex spoken messages d325 Communicating with - receiving written messages d320 Communicating with - receiving formal sign language messages
following one- or two-step oral instructions to carry out a task The ability to carry out very short and simple instructions.	b1641 Organization and planning	d163 Thinking d210 Undertaking a single task d310 Communicating with - receiving spoken messages d3100 Communicating with - receiving simple spoken messages d320 Communicating with - receiving formal sign language messages d325 Communicating with - receiving written messages
describing work activity to someone else	b167 Mental functions of language b1671 Expression of spoken language	d330 Speaking d3302 Producing complex spoken messages d340 Producing messages in formal sign language d345 writing messages d360 Using communication devices and techniques
asking and answering questions and providing explanations	b167 Mental functions of language b1670 Reception of language b1671 Expression of spoken language	d138 Acquiring information d310-d329 Communicating - receiving d330-d349 Communicating - producing d330 Speaking d350 Conversation d355 Discussion

recognizing a mistake and correcting it	b1644 Insight b1643 Cognitive flexibility b1646 Problem solving	d163 Thinking d175 Solving problems
identifying and solving problems	b1646 Problem Solving	d175 Solving problems
sequencing multi-step activities	b164 Higher-level cognitive functions	d210 Undertaking a single task d220 Undertaking multiple tasks
using reason and judgment to make work-related decisions The ability to make simple work-related decisions	b1602 Content of thought b164 Higher-level cognitive functions b1644 Insight b1645 Judgement	d177 Making decisions d240 Handling stress and other psychological demands d2400 Handling responsibilities

Table 3 includes the mapping of the B2 Criterion and area C of the Mental RFC, which refer to the abilities to relate to and work with supervisors, co-workers, and the public, to ICF codes.

Table 3: SSA B2 Criterion and Mental RFC Area C: Interact with others

12.00 Mental Disorders - Adult	ICF Codes	
SSA B2 Criterion Mental RFC Assessment - C	ICF b codes Body Function	ICF d codes Activities Functioning
abilities to relate to and work with supervisors, co-workers, and the public The ability to get along with coworkers or peers without distracting them or exhibiting behavioral extremes The ability to interact appropriately with the general public	b122 Global psychosocial functions b126 Temperament and personality functions b1261 Agreeableness	d710 Basic interpersonal interactions d7100 Respect and warmth in relationships d7101 Appreciation in relationships d7102 Tolerance in relationships d7103 Criticism in relationships d7104 Social cues in relationships d7105 Physical contact in relationships d7106 Differentiation of familiar persons d720 Complex interpersonal interactions d7200 Forming relationships d7201 Terminating relationships d7202 Regulating behaviors within interactions d7203 Interacting according to social rules d730 Relating with strangers d740 Formal relationships d7400 Relating with persons in authority d7401 Relating with subordinates d7402 Relating with equals

		d750 Informal social relationships d7504 Informal relationships with peers
cooperating with others	b122 Global psychosocial functions b126 Temperament and personality functions b1261 Agreeableness	d710 Basic interpersonal interactions d7100 Respect and warmth in relationships d7102 Tolerance in relationships d7103 Criticism in relationships d720 Complex interpersonal interactions d7200 Forming relationships d7202 Regulating behaviors within interactions d7203 Interacting according to social rules d730 Relating with strangers d740 Formal relationships d750 Informal social relationships
asking for help when needed The ability to ask simple questions or request assistance	b126 Temperament and personality functions b1266 Confidence b164 Higher-level cognitive functions b1644 Insight b167 Mental functions of language	d138 Acquiring information d330 Speaking d3301 Producing simple spoken messages d3302 Producing complex spoken messages d710 Basic interpersonal interactions d7100 Respect and warmth in relationships d7101 Appreciation in relationships d720 Complex interpersonal interactions d7203 Interacting according to social rules d730 Relating with strangers d740 Formal relationships d750 Informal social relationships
handling conflicts with others	b122 Global psychosocial functions b126 Temperament and personality functions b1266 Confidence b164 Higher-level cognitive functions b1643 Cognitive flexibility	d175 Solving problems d240 Handling stress and other psychological demands d710 Basic interpersonal interactions d7102 Tolerance in relationships d7103 Criticism in relationships d720 Complex interpersonal interactions d740 Formal relationships d750 Informal social relationships
stating own point of view	b126 Temperament and personality functions b1266 Confidence b167 Mental functions of language	d330 Speaking d3302 Producing complex spoken messages
initiating or sustaining conversation	b122 Global psychosocial functions b167 Mental functions of language	d330-d349 Communicating - producing d350 Conversation

		d3501 Sustaining a conversation
understanding and responding to social cues (physical, verbal, emotional)	b122 Global psychosocial functions b167 Mental functions of language	d315 Communicating with - receiving - nonverbal messages d335 Producing nonverbal messages d3350 Producing body language d710 Basic interpersonal interactions d7104 Social cues in relationships d7105 Physical contact in relationships d720 Complex interpersonal interactions d7203 Interacting according to social rules d7204 Maintaining social space
responding to requests, suggestions, criticism, correction, and challenges The ability to accept instructions and respond appropriately to criticism from supervisors.	b164 Higher-level cognitive functions b1643 Cognitive flexibility b1644 Insight	d710 Basic interpersonal interactions d7103 Criticism in relationships d720 Complex interpersonal interactions d7202 Regulating behaviors within interactions d7203 Interacting according to social rules d740 Formal relationships
keeping social interactions free of excessive irritability, sensitivity, argumentativeness or suspiciousness	b126 Temperament and personality functions b1261 Agreeableness b1263 Psychic stability b152 Emotional functions b1520 Appropriateness of emotion b1521 Regulation of emotion	d720 Complex interpersonal interactions d7202 Regulating behaviors within interactions d7203 Interacting according to social rules
The ability to maintain socially appropriate behavior	b164 Higher-level cognitive functions b1644 Insight	d710 Basic interpersonal interactions d7101 Appreciation in relationships d7102 Tolerance in relationships d7103 Criticism in relationships d7104 Social cues in relationships d7105 Physical contact in relationships d7106 Differentiation of familiar persons d720 Complex interpersonal interactions d7200 Forming relationships d7201 Terminating relationships d7202 Regulating behaviors within interactions d7203 Interacting according to social rules
...adhere to basic standards of neatness and cleanliness	b114 Orientation Functions b164 Higher-level cognitive functions b1645 Judgement	d177 Making decisions d720 Complex interpersonal interactions

Table 4 includes the mapping of the B3 Criterion and area B of the Mental RFC, which refer to the abilities to focus attention on work activities and stay on task at a sustained rate, to ICF codes.

Table 4: SSA B3 Criterion and Mental RFC Area B: Concentrate, persist, or maintain pace

12.00 Mental Disorders - Adult	ICF Codes	
SSA B3 Criterion Mental RFC Assessment - B	ICF b codes Body Function	ICF d codes Activities Functioning
abilities to focus attention on work activities and stay on task at a sustained rate The ability to maintain attention and concentration for extended periods	b130 Energy and drive functions b140 Attention functions b1400 Sustaining attention	d160 Focusing attention d210 Undertaking a single task d220 Undertaking multiple tasks d230 Carrying out daily routine d2303 Managing one's own activity level
initiating and performing a task that you understand and know how to do	b164 Higher level-cognitive functions b1641 Organization and planning	d210 Undertaking a single task d220 Undertaking multiple tasks d230 Carrying out daily routine
working at an appropriate and consistent pace	b130 Energy and drive functions b1300 Energy level	d210 Undertaking a single task d220 Undertaking multiple tasks d230 Carrying out daily routine d2303 Managing one's own activity level
completing tasks in a timely manner	b1140 Orientation to time b164 Higher level cognitive functions b1642 Time management	d210 Undertaking a single task d220 Undertaking multiple tasks d230 Carrying out daily routine d2302 Completing the daily routine d2301 Managing daily routine d2303 Managing one's own activity level
ignoring or avoiding distractions while working	b140 Attention functions	d160 Focusing attention
changing activities or work settings without being disruptive	b126 Temperament and personality functions b1261 Agreeableness b164 Higher-level cognitive functions b1643 Cognitive flexibility	d177 Making decisions d230 Carrying out a daily routine d2304 Adapting to changes in daily routine d240 Handling stress and other psychological demands
working close to or with others without interrupting or distracting them	b130 Energy and drive functions	d160 focusing attention d177 Making decisions

The ability to work in coordination with or proximity to others without being distracted by them.	b1304 Impulse control b140 Attention functions	d210 Undertaking single tasks d2103 Undertaking a single task in a group d220 Undertaking multiple tasks d2203 Undertaking multiple tasks in a group d240 Handling stress and other psychological demands
sustaining an ordinary routine and regular attendance at work The ability to perform activities within a schedule, maintain regular attendance and be punctual within customary tolerances. The ability to sustain an ordinary routine without special supervision.	b130 Energy and drive functions	d230 Carrying out a daily routine d2301 Managing daily routine d2302 Completing the daily routine d2303 Managing one's own activity level d2304 Adapting to changes in daily routine d240 Handling stress and other psychological demands d2400 Handling responsibilities
working a full day without needing more than the allotted number or length of rest periods during the day The ability to complete a normal workday and workweek without interruptions from psychologically based symptoms Perform at a consistent pace without an unreasonable number and length of rest periods.	b130 Energy and drive functions	d230 Carrying out daily routine d2301 Managing daily routine d2302 Completing the daily routine d2303 Managing one's own activity level d2304 Adapting to changes in daily routine d240 Handling stress and other psychological demands

Table 5 includes the mapping of the B4 Criterion and area D of the Mental RFC, which refer to the abilities to regulate emotions, control behavior, and maintain well-being in a work setting, to ICF codes.

Table 5: SSA B4 Criterion and Mental RFC Area D: Adapt or manage oneself

12.00 Mental Disorders - Adult	ICF Codes	
SSA B4 Criterion Mental RFC Assessment - D	ICF b codes Body Function	ICF d codes Activities Functioning
responding to demands	b126 Temperament and personality functions b164 Higher-level cognitive functions	d240 Handling stress and other psychological demands d2400 Handling responsibilities d2401 Handling stress d2402 Handling crisis
adapting to changes	b164 Higher-level cognitive functions	d230 Carrying out daily routine d2304 Adapting to changes in daily routine

The ability to respond appropriately to changes in the work setting	b1643 Cognitive flexibility	d240 Handling stress and other psychological demands d2401 Handling stress
managing your psychologically based symptoms	b164 Higher-level cognitive functions b1641 Organization and planning b1644 Insight	d240 Handling stress and other psychological demands d2401 Handling stress d570 Looking after one's health
distinguishing between acceptable and unacceptable work performance	b164 Higher-level cognitive functions b1644 Insight b1645 Judgement	d163 Thinking d177 Making decisions
setting realistic goals The ability to set realistic goals	b164 Higher-level cognitive functions b1641 Organization and planning b1645 Judgement	d163 Thinking
making plans for yourself independently of others The ability to make plans independently of others	b164 Higher-level cognitive functions b1641 Organization and planning b1602 Content of thought	d163 Thinking
maintaining personal hygiene and attire appropriate to a work setting	b114 Orientation functions b164 higher level cognitive functions b1645 Judgement	d177 Making decisions
being aware of normal hazards and taking appropriate precautions The ability to be aware of normal hazards and take appropriate precautions	b164 higher level cognitive functions b1644 Insight b1645 Judgement	d177 Making decisions d240 Handling stress and other psychological demands d2401 Handling stress d2402 Handling crisis
The ability to travel in unfamiliar places or use public transportation	b114 Orientation functions b1641 Organization and planning	d175 Solving problems d177 Making decisions d220 Undertaking multiple tasks d2101 Undertaking a complex task d470 Using transportation

Table 6 includes the mapping of the C1 Criterion, ongoing reliance on medical treatment, mental health therapy, psychosocial support(s), or a highly structured setting(s), to diminish the symptoms and signs of the mental disorder, to the relevant ICF codes.

Table 6: SSA C1 Criterion

12.00 Mental Disorders - Adult	ICF Codes	
SSA C1 Criterion	ICF b codes Body Function	ICF d codes Activities Functioning
Ongoing reliance on medical treatment, psychosocial support(s), or a highly structured setting(s), to diminish the symptoms and signs of the mental disorder.	n/a	d570 Looking after one's health
mental health therapy,	n/a	d570 Looking after one's health
psychosocial support(s),	n/a	d570 Looking after one's health
highly structured setting(s),	n/a	none

Table 7 includes the mapping of the C2 Criterion, minimal capacity to adapt to changes in one's environment or to demands that are not already part of one's daily life, or unable to function outside of one's home or a more restrictive setting without substantial psychosocial supports, to the relevant ICF codes.

Table 7: SSA C2 Criterion

12.00 Mental Disorders - Adult	ICF Codes	
SSA C2 Criterion	ICF b codes Body Function	ICF d codes Activities Functioning
Minimal capacity to adapt to changes in one's environment	b164 Higher-level cognitive functions	d240 Handling stress and other psychological demands
Minimal capacity to adapt to demands that are not already part of one's daily life.	b164 Higher-level cognitive functions	d2304 Adapting to changes in daily routine
changes or increased demands have led to exacerbation of symptoms and signs and to deterioration in functioning.	b164 Higher-level cognitive functions	d240 Handling stress and other psychological demands
Unable to function outside of one's home or a more restrictive setting, without substantial psychosocial supports	b164 Higher-level cognitive functions	d240 Handling stress and other psychological demands d210 Undertaking a single task

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